

CHOOSING INTERESTING AND MEANINGFUL TOPICS IN THE TEACHING OF VISUAL ARTS, AWAKENING STUDENTS' INTEREST IN VISUAL ARTS

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Annotation. This article fully describes the methods of using modern pedagogical technologies in the organization of fine art classes, the application of pedagogical renewal processes in educational practice, the issue of pedagogical technologies in teaching fine arts at school.

Key words: fine arts, pedagogical technologies, renewal, thematic composition.

It is known that the driving force of man and his society is human thinking. Thinking is a complex of intelligence and worldly knowledge.

Among all stages, we must know that there are many tasks in terms of qualities, such as being able to correctly understand and explain the aspects of interaction with the educational process of fine art, applied art, architecture, sculpture.

We all know that the rapid penetration of foreign experiences into the educational system of our country, new educational concepts (global education, child-friendly attitude, exclusive educational pedagogical technologies, etc.) have aroused unprecedented interest among teachers, experts in methodology, pedagogy, educational psychology. Innovations in the field of education have not been able to create the same treatment for all teachers. Our observations show that young teachers are concerned about their professional future, and some older teachers (approaching retirement age) are apathetic.

The implementation of the renewal processes in pedagogy in educational practice is one of the complex, multifaceted problems and has its own characteristics. Education is a social system that applies to all components of the educational process. In this, the activity of the student and the teacher, the purpose, content, method, form, result, conditions, technologies and management of the process are effectively affected.

Multifaceted problems that enter educational practice indirectly, that is, teacher skills through didactic tools, educational technologies. Implementation of computer and information communication technologies, thus equipping all teachers with computer literacy and information communication technologies skills. In addition to strengthening professional skills, in accordance with the above-mentioned instructions, it is necessary to pay attention to the following in order to increase the effectiveness of visual art classes and increase students' interest in science.

Choosing interesting and meaningful topics in the teaching of visual arts will increase students' interest in visual arts. Currently, students in schools are not limited to using drawing books, paints, pencils, pencils and erasers, but using modern, foreign technologies, several types of paints, colored pencils, and various drawing tools that increase the brightness of decorative works can be used. It activates students' artistic activity with such objects. It arouses interest in art.

In the field of education, it is necessary to study a specific didactic process in order to use pedagogical technology in the teaching of visual arts and to achieve its effectiveness. Until now, there has not been any more systematic scientific work or methodical-didactic manual published on the issue of pedagogical technology in teaching visual arts at school. Therefore, in thinking about this issue, we found it necessary to study the issue more widely and analyze the issue of technology, pedagogical technology, and then the use of pedagogical technology in the teaching of visual arts.

It is known that visual arts classes are carried out in five types of classes or technologies:

1. Drawing based on the object.
2. Work on the thematic composition.
3. Decorative applied art.
4. Sculpture works.
5. Classes are conducted on the basis of art studies.

Although the technology of these classes has the same content, the teaching technology in them is definitely different from each other. That is, in the classes "drawing a picture by looking at the object itself", it is depicted from nature, seeing the object itself, as far as the form is possible.

In the thematic composition, students think, look into the distance, and draw a picture on the basis of remembering something.

In sculpting, the basis of the training is the technology of physical labor, not with pencils and paints, but with clay and plasticine. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to the definition of pedagogical technologies in visual art classes and their classification into "Lesson technology" types.

Pedagogical technology of fine art is a pedagogical process that can guarantee the achievement of a predetermined goal and the fulfillment of this task based on the tools of a fine art teacher to provide students with art knowledge and skills in a certain period and conditions. That is, it is a pedagogical process that provides guaranteed results on the basis of a set of didactic, methodical and methodological processes of using educational and training tools to achieve the set and intended goal of the teacher's 45 minutes of the lesson.

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